

THE IMPORTANCE OF MUSIC EDUCATION IN ORGANIZING INSTRUMENT ENSEMBLES

Abdurazzokov Abdullojon Abdugoffor ugli

Namangan State Pedagogical Institute

2nd year master's degree in "Music Education and Art".

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11029703>

Abstract: The role of music in the upbringing of a perfect generation is incomparable. Music, unlike other forms of art, is a wonderful tool capable of using the most delicate human feelings, emotions, rich emotional reserves in a person. In the content of this article, opinions were expressed regarding the organizational structure of musical instrument training and specific methodological aspects of working on musical works.

Key words: music, listening to music, instrument performance, ensemble, melody, rhythm, line, genre, aesthetic education, taste, technical performance, artistic performance.

Introduction.

The future of independent Uzbekistan largely depends on raising a young generation with full potential. In order to realize such an urgent task, it is important to study the rich historical experience of the Uzbek people in terms of education and to apply it to life in the formation and education of a modern person. The art of music, as an important factor of aesthetic education, has a strong influence on personality formation. Proper organization of music lessons in the family, kindergarten, school is an effective way to enrich the inner world of the young generation and to understand art correctly.

Music education is a component of aesthetic education. Education is one of the leading factors that shape a person's personality. Aesthetic education, as its component, is based on the doctrine of the essence of beauty, the unity of aesthetic and moral feelings, the nationalism of art, expands and deepens students' knowledge of the objective world, develops their creative ability and desire. develops taste and helps them to develop high spiritual qualities.

Music expresses human feelings, hopes, desires in its own artistic language and actively affects human emotions.

Music is both science and art. It is based on physics and mathematics, which make music a science. But you can't look at a piece of music as a static concept of this science. Because music is a living art that is always developing. The art of music becomes a companion of a person from the first years of his life and makes a significant contribution to the general cultural development. Music is a

constant companion of human life. According to scientist Stendhal, music is one of the forms of art that can penetrate deep into a person's heart and reflect his inner experiences.

"Music belongs to the system of expressive art. Music also expresses events. But it is not determined by the dimensions of space and material objects, as in architecture. Music is perceived not by sight, but by hearing. Since the theme of music has its own characteristics and cannot cover all aspects of a person and reality, it primarily expresses the inner spiritual world of a person, his feelings and mood... music creates an emotional image of reality." .

Music has a wide range of mood expression. Human mood is a complex emotion that is not connected to anything. Mood has a generalized character, secondary aspects are excluded from it, and the most important aspects that determine the emotional attitude of a person to reality are distinguished. The power of music is that it can show happiness, sadness, imagination, endurance, courage, depression and similar human mental states in a private and general way, in their interdependence, in their absorption into each other. The language of music represents the unity of all parts, the form of the work. Form is a material expression of musical content. The composer's thoughts, feelings, and imagination reach the listeners through the musical form.

Therefore, it opens a wide way to acquire the "language" of music, to understand its essence, to master the wealth of thoughts, feelings, and experiences in music. Ancient thinkers emphasized the importance of musical education for the growing generation. The human and positive qualities of a future member of society are formed right from childhood. It was during this period that music was considered a means of forming positive qualities. Music also arises in the composition of singing and dancing, and later becomes an independent type of artistic creation, has a very specific "language" of artistic expression, specially developed and selected sounds are the source of this "language".

Of course, music does not determine by itself the directions of personality formation and its positive qualities. The most important aspects of the educational effect depend on the ideological content of the musical work. Thus, the tasks of musical-aesthetic education are determined. The famous Polish composer K. Szymanowski in his article "Educational value of music in society", talking about the natural power of music, he said that it can be used in two opposite directions - to create and destroy - "directing it to the necessary work,

quickly "It is necessary to use the power of music effectively, just like using the waters of the flowing river for useful and productive work, i.e. to turn the mill."

The impact of music on a person, its role in the spiritual life of an individual and society is a complex problem. This complexity and sophistication did not come to science immediately. At this point, it is appropriate to recall Asafev's words: "...music is both an art, a science, a language, and a game."

Therefore, the role of music in the formation of musical and personal characteristics of children is incomparable. Music affects a person in every way: the melody and its musical expression have a deep impact on a person's emotions, evoke different feelings and create different moods. The text and ideological content of the song affects not only the emotions, but also the minds of the listeners, excites them and makes them think. It creates a certain attitude in people towards the spiritual problems reflected in the work. Such influence is very complex and powerful.

Ensuring the continuity of education in the field of musical education is of special importance. First of all, primary and general secondary schools in the 1-7th grades of music culture are aiming to attract students who have a talent for music to children's music and art schools (of course after their school lessons), and in the future, music It guarantees the training of qualified specialists (personnel) in the field. After the children's music and art school, the future music teachers who have graduated from the music (art) faculties of art colleges and higher educational institutions will have strong skills in reading notes and playing instruments.

The formation of work on musical works has a positive effect on the development of musical interests and abilities of students, as well as a great help in the growth of their musical-theoretical literacy, the improvement of music perception, description, analysis, and performance skills. will give.

There are real opportunities to organize musical performances and turn their training into a natural continuation of educational work in the field of musical education. Because, for example, we are forced to rely on theoretical information when teaching to play the rubob instrument. Without it, it is extremely difficult to bring the students who have joined the ensemble to a uniform and uniform (close to each other) level of playing.

In this place, it is necessary to clearly express the rhythm (counting), the placement of sounds in the rubab curtains, mediator beats, sound extension-counting, creating different tones (accent), mastering strokes such as tremolo, liga, ligato, staccato, musical character It is a natural necessity to have a stock of

accurate knowledge of tempo and dynamic tones for expression. This in itself provides an opportunity to deepen the theoretical material learned in music lessons. When music lessons are done well, students engage in more music and practice more than their peers. This leads them to relatively successfully participate in the activities of music literacy, listening to music, singing in a choir, and demonstrate their knowledge.

Playing a musical instrument, accompanying, listening to others, playing together, observing the performance of others, following the teacher's practical instructions, completing the observed shortcomings together, observing the rhythm, ensemble, all these develop the musical memory and performance skills of the participants - students. has a great impact on development.

After the ensemble participants have thoroughly mastered the elementary rules, requirements, and elements of playing the rubab, they remember the instructions given by the teacher (leader) to independently perform the tasks given to them, to learn the pieces. They can learn independently, improve performance techniques and skills. Ensemble participants learn Uzbek folk tunes of various genres and characters, tunes and songs written for children by modern composers, works of sister nations, foreign composers, and folk music, and their musical outlook and thinking develop.

Organizing the listening of various folk, classical, works of some composers with the ensemble members, going to concerts together, participating in various events, discussing achievements and successes after the performance increases their responsibility for mastering the performance of the instrument. it accustoms them to be disciplined and lays the groundwork for them to learn well in other subjects as well.

Listening to a certain work before studying it, then sharing the students' impressions about this work, the teacher's explanatory words, brief comments, conversations about the content, genre, structure, character, melody (melody) of the works), allows to have a correct idea about the rhythm and harmony. This is a real interest in art and attachment to it, as well as aesthetic education itself.

According to their purpose and essence, the musical education direction, music school instrumental performance and ensemble or amateur clubs include the following tasks:

- ❖ ideological aesthetic education of students;
- ❖ to realize students' musical interests and abilities, to develop the culture of singing and performance;
- ❖ performing in an ensemble, teaching to sing as a team;

- ❖ to strengthen the knowledge and skills acquired in the course of training;
- ❖ improving the artistic performance skills of participants, preparing students for concert performance.

Specific methodological aspects of working on musical works:

- ❖ To distinguish between hearing music and listening to music while working on musical works, and to study the sources of analytical analysis of music;
- ❖ The rarest classical music works belonging to the Uzbek people are included in the music listening program. If the students' artistic taste turns in this direction;
- ❖ If the complexity of the musical works, which are called examples of "common culture" far from national melodies, is explained to teenagers;
- ❖ If the psychological characteristics of students are taken into account when organizing the process of musical performance;
- ❖ Possibilities of teaching students to listen to music in the performance of musical instruments will be explored, and new methods will be used.

After all, music serves to form the spiritual, artistic and moral culture of the young generation, to realize national pride and patriotism, to expand the scope of thought, to grow creative skills and artistic taste, to educate independence and initiative.

References:

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoev. We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people. T.O. 2017.
2. Decision PQ-2909 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 "On measures to further develop the higher education system". www.lex.uz.
3. M. Gafurov. Instrument performance. Tashkent, 2015
4. Saipova D. Improving the process of acquiring musical-theoretical knowledge. T.: Science and Technology Publishing House, 2005, -84 pages.
5. Panjiev Q.B. Improvement of professional training of future music teachers by means of Uzbek folk singing. Monograph. T.: Makhalla and family publishing house. 2021. – 200
6. Panjiyev Qurboniyoz Berdievich "Uzbek Seasonal Ceremony" European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education Vol. 2 No. 4 (2022): European Journal of Innovation in Nonformal Education <http://innovatus.es/index.php/ejine/issue/view/14>

FRANCE

FRANCE

7. Panjiyev Qurbonniyoz Berdiyevich “Components For Improving The Professional Training Of Future Music Teachers” International Journal of Pedagogics Vol. 2No. 04 (2022); <https://theusajournals.com/index.php/ijp/>

